

POLYGLOT ISHAKHAN IBRAT'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE WORLD LINGUISTICS

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ABSTRACT

*In this scientific article highlights about the contributions of
Ishakhan Ibrat.*

During the years of independence of Uzbekistan, the creative activity of our great ancestor Ibrat is widely studied due to the great attention of our President Shavkat Mirziyoev. On the initiative of the head of the state, opening a school which is specialized in teaching foreign languages such as Russian, English, German, French, Arabic, Korean and Turkish provided a golden opportunity to explore Ibrat's creative wealth popular-scientifically. Likewise, the museum, a modern and large avenue and the printing house were established under his name in Turakurgan, the birthplace of our great-grandfather Ibrat. Nowadays, information about Ibrat is being published in popular-scientific publications, announced on radio broadcasts and telecasted on television. Almost all his historical works and scientific

manuscripts have been published and famous scientists are doing research on them with strong interest.

I studied at boarding school named after Ibrat and Ibrat¹ focused his attention on the progress of Uzbek linguistics during his activity. At the beginning of the twentieth century, diplomatic, commercial, scientific and cultural relations throughout the countries of the world reached its peak, so knowing language well was very vital to make Turkestan developed country. At that time a person who did not know any language well or an uneducated one lagged behind worldly knowledge and even a century. For that reason, Ibrat started composing a dictionary for learning Uzbek and foreign languages, fortunately he managed it. At the beginning of the twentieth century, significant changes took

place in the capitalistic system of development around the world. Even in remote areas such as Turkestan, the local population made noticeable efforts to the social, economic and cultural growth. There was also a growing interest for the Russian language among the locals in Turkestan. "Russo-native" schools and "new method" schools of the country were operated in urban areas (Tashkent, Samarkand, Fergana) and then in rural areas. However, learning Russian was limited, since there were no Russian dictionaries, textbooks or manuals available. In this case, "Turkestanskiy Vedomosti"² ("Turkic Gazette") said, "There is an increasing number of Russian-learning people in the city these days. It is important to emphasize that the indigenous inhabitants have a considerable ability to learn foreign languages" [1].

Indeed, "Advanced intellectuals, traders and artisans had an interest in acquiring knowledge of Russian and other languages, but there were no manuals for learning and teaching languages, all of which were written in Cyrillic and Latin..." [3] Ishakhan Ibrat, who had detailed knowledge of Russian, the languages of the West, the Middle East and the Asian nations, dealt with that problem by writing six-language dictionary called "Lug'ati sittati al-sina" ("A six-language dictionary"). The book contained translations of Arabic, Persian, Hindi, Turkish, Uzbek (Sartiq) and Russian words. Before Ibrat, there were dictionaries that were in Turkic - Arabic languages written by Makhmud Kashghari and Makhmud Zamakhshari. [2]

A highly gifted Ibrat also used the Russian words in Arabic script to make it easier to

understand for those who did not know Russian writing. Composing such kind of dictionary was extremely complex job, nonetheless it had positive results.

The man, who familiarized himself with the manuscript of the book, commented to the "Turkiston viloyati gazetisi" ("The Gazette of Turkestan region"): "Although this book named "Lug'ati sittati alsina" was small, there was no one in Turkestan region who had the ability to classify a language dictionary. Therefore, we wrote to the newspaper hoping that "Six-language dictionary" which Mister Judge - Ibrat sent to the publication would be allowed to be come out.

I read the dictionary with care and love,

Thus I gave opinions above".[3]

The development of human speech plays a major role in the communication of nations. Ibrat's scientific work on the development of linguistics, his striving for progress to be found rarely from other linguists' activities. Worldwide travels and more researches broadened Ibrat's outlook towards life and education, afterwards he wrote a valuable work named "History of books" ("Jome ul-xutut"). The aforementioned book was devoted to the history of writings. It consists of 132 pages. Precious information on 41 world scripts was given in that historical book. The book was published in the printing house that Ibrat himself set up.

Ibrat said, "When going to the pharmacy, Latin is needed, English is required to write letters to India, otherwise letters will not be accepted and writing in French is essential in Iran. Russian writing is what we need first, it is the main requirement for

Turkestan people. Let judges and teachers not to deny it".[5]

Ibrahim Davron, a contemporary of Ibrat, wrote about him: "Ibrat was a great calligrapher who had beautiful handwriting".[4]

It is clear that there were "Russian-Sartic(Uzbek)", "Sartic(Uzbek)-Russian" dictionaries of V. Nalivkin and his wife M. Nalivkin till "Lug'atti sittati alsina". The advantage of the dictionary of Ibrat is that it was written in Arabic script not in Cyrillic.

Iskhakhan Ibrat is not dead, he is alive and he lives in our hearts forever. It is said that there is no grave of the best person who

only did good deeds, because the best people like Ibrat are buried in the hearts. Ibrat's great work is being pursued by his followers. The school of Ibrat aims to teach seven languages of the world ,in other words, Russian, English, German, French, Arabic, Korean, Turkish and improve the art of translation.

¹ Ibrat – The pseudonym of Ishakhan. It means 'Пример' in Russian and 'Example' in English.

²"Turkestanskiy Vedomosti" – the first daily Russian newspaper in Turkestan.

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